

BIR JINSLI BENNEY-LUKE TIPIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMA UCHUN VART BO'YICHA NOLOKAL MASALA

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada $D_t^\rho V(t) + A(D_t^\rho V(t)) + A^2(D_t^\rho V(t)) + AV(t) = 0$, $0 < \rho < 1$ ko'rinishidagi kasr tartibli tenglama uchun vaqt bo'yicha $0 < t < T$, $V(T) = \chi V(+0) + \psi$ nolokal shartni qanotlantruvchi yechimni topish masalasi o'rganilgan, bu yerda χ va T , berilgan sonlar. Maqolada χ parametrni yechimning mavjudligi va yagonaligiga ta'siri o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Nolokal masala, Hilbert fazosi, Benney-Luke tipidagi tenglama, Caputo ma'nosidagi hosila

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается задача нахождения решения дробного дифференциального уравнения вида $D_t^\rho V(t) + A(D_t^\rho V(t)) + A^2(D_t^\rho V(t)) + AV(t) = 0$, $0 < \rho < 1$, удовлетворяющего по времени нелокальным условиям $0 < t < T$, $V(T) = \chi V(+0) + \psi$, где χ и T — заданные числа. В работе изучается влияние параметра χ на существование и единственность решения.

Ключевые слова и выражения: нелокальные задачи, производные Хильфера, уравнения типа Бенни — Люка, производная Капуто, обратные задачи.

Abstract. This paper studies the problem of finding a solution satisfying the non-local conditions $0 < t < T$, $V(T) = \chi V(+0) + \psi$ with respect to time is studied for the fractional-order equation of the form $D_t^\rho V(t) + A(D_t^\rho V(t)) + A^2(D_t^\rho V(t)) + AV(t) = 0$, $0 < \rho < 1$, where χ and T are given constants. The influence of the parameter χ on the existence and uniqueness of the solution is investigated in the article.

Keywords and phrases: Non-local problems, the Hilfer derivatives, Benney-Luke type equations, Caputo, inverse problems.

Aytaylik, $h(t)$ vektor funksiya $[0, +\infty)$ da aniqlangan bo'lsin. $h(t)$ funksiyaning Caputo ma'nosida ρ kasr tartibli hosilasi esa quyidagicha ko'rinishda aniqlanadi:

$$I_t^\rho h(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\rho)} \int_0^t \frac{h'(\xi)}{(t-\xi)^\rho} d\xi, \quad t > 0,$$

bu yerda $\Gamma(\beta)$ - Eylerning gamma funksiyasi.

Quyidagi masalani qaraylik

$$\begin{cases} D_t^\rho V(t) + A(D_t^\rho V(t)) + A^2(D_t^\rho V(t)) + AV(t) = 0, & 0 < t < T; \\ V(T) = \chi V(+0) + \psi. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

bu yerda $f(t) \in C([0, T]; H)$, $\psi \in H$ berilgan funksiyalar va χ o'zgarmas son.

Aytaylik, H separabl Hilbert fazosi va $A: H \rightarrow H$ operator $D(A) \subset H$ aniqlanish sohasiga ega o'z-o'ziga qo'shma, musbat, chegaralanmagan ixtiyoriy operator bo'lsin. Faraz qilaylik, A operator H fazoda to'la ortonormal $\{v_k\}$ xos funksiyalar sistemasiga va mos ravishda $\{\lambda_k\}$ musbat xos sonlar to'plamiga ega bo'lsin. Shu bilan birga A operator xos sonlari ketma-ketligi noldan boshqa limit nuqtaga ega bo'lmasin. Xos qiymatlarni qayta nomerlash yordamida ularni kamaymaydigan qilib nomerlab olamiz, ya'ni $0 < \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \rightarrow +\infty$ kabi yozib olamiz.

Keling, H Hilbert fazosida A operatorning darajasi tushunchasini eslatib o'taylik. τ ixtiyoriy haqiqiy son bo'lsin. Biz H da A operatorning darajasini quyidagicha kiritamiz:

$$A^\tau h = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^\tau h_k v_k,$$

bu yerda $h_k = (h, v_k)$ lar $h \in H$ elementning Furye koeffitsiyentlari. Ushbu operatorning aniqlanish sohasi quyidagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi

$$D(A^\tau) = \{h \in H : \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^{2\tau} |h_k|^2 < \infty\}.$$

$h \in D(A^\tau)$ element uchun normani quyidagicha kiritamiz

$$\|h\|_\tau^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k^{2\tau} |h_k|^2 = \|A^\tau h\|^2$$

va bu norma bilan birgalikda $D(A^\tau)$ Hilbert fazosiga aylanadi.

$C((0, T); H)$ orqali qiymatlari H da yotuvchi $t \in (0, T)$ oraliqda uzluksiz $V(t)$ funksiyalar to'plamini belgilaymiz.

Ta'rif. Agar $V(t) \in AC([0, T]; H)$ funksiya $A^2(D_t^\rho V(t)), A(D_t^\rho V(t)), D_t^\rho V(t), AV(t) \in C((0, T); H)$ xossalarga ega bo'lib, (1) masalaning shartlarini qanotlanrsa u holda bu funksiya (1) nolokal masalaning yechimi deyiladi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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